

S₆: The whole enchelada and more

Adolf Cusmariu
Email: adolcus@gmail.com

A previous article [1] detailed generation of the symmetric group S₄ through column-swap operations on a single parent tag-matrix; several such turned out to be available for S₆, hence computations were considerably more extensive to generate its 720 elements.

To recall, S₂ is composed of the set

$$s_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad s_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

while the six elements of S₃ are

$$p_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad p_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad p_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad p_4 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad p_5 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad p_6 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The 24 Kronecker-evolved parents are, for j = 1,2,...6:

kron(s₀,p_j) ≡ s₀p_j, kron(s₁,p_j) ≡ s₁p_j:

$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$

and 'flips' kron(p_j,s₀) ≡ p_js₀, kron(p_j,s₁) ≡ p_js₁:

$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$

However, only 22 are unique:

$s0p1 = p1s0 = I_6$, the 6x6 identity matrix, and

$s1p2 = p2s1 = C_6$, the 6x6 counter (or skew) identity matrix

All parent matrices are orthogonal; except for $s0p5$, $s0p6$, $s1p5$, $s1p6$, $p5s0$, $p6s0$, $p5s1$ and $p6s1$, the other 14 matrices are also symmetric and idempotent.

A tag notation introduced for S_4 [1] will also be used here; thus 231564 stands for $s0p5$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

OCTAVE code to produce this particular tag is below:

```
for k=1:6,ct(k)=find(s0p5(k,:)==1);,end,sprintf("%i",ct)
```

To recover matrix $s0p5$ from its column-tag vector $\{ct(k)\}$, $k=1, 2, \dots, 6$, do

```
for k=1:6,s0p5(k,ct(k))=1;end
```

As previously noted, there is a one-to-one correspondence between tags and (0,1) matrices.

The table below lists all 24 column-tags; 'direct' parents in green, 'flips' in yellow.

kron	tag	kron	tag
s0p1	123456	p1s0	123456
s0p2	321654	p2s0	563412
s0p3	213546	p3s0	341256
s0p4	132465	p4s0	125634
s0p5	231564	p5s0	345612
s0p6	312645	p6s0	561234
s1p1	456123	p1s1	214365
s1p2	654321	p2s1	654321
s1p3	546213	p3s1	432165
s1p4	465132	p4s1	216543
s1p5	564231	p5s1	436521
s1p6	645312	p6s1	652143

S_6 tag genealogies follow; parents evolve radially outward (no cluttering arrows) from the center S_2 doublets through S_3 triplets.

The tables below list Kronecker parents and complement tags.

kron	comp	kron	comp
s0p1 123456	s1p2 654321	p1s0 123456	p2s1 654321
s0p2 321654	s1p1 456123	p2s0 563412	p1s1 214365
s0p3 213546	s1p5 564231	p3s0 341256	p5s1 436521
s0p4 132465	s1p6 645312	p4s0 125634	p6s1 652143
s0p5 231564	s1p3 546213	p5s0 345612	p3s1 432165
s0p6 312645	s1p4 465132	p6s0 561234	p4s1 216543

Partial Cayley tables are below, first among 'direct', and then 'flip' parents; the identity matrix is in yellow, the skew in green.

*	s0p2	s0p3	s0p4	s0p5	s0p6	s1p1	s1p2	s1p3	s1p4	s1p5	s1p6
s0p2	s0p1	s0p6	s0p5	s0p4	s0p3	s1p2	s1p1	s1p6	s1p5	s1p4	s1p3
s0p3	s0p5	s0p1	s0p6	s0p2	s0p4	s1p3	s1p5	s1p1	s1p6	s1p2	s1p4
s0p4	s0p6	s0p5	s0p1	s0p3	s0p2	s1p4	s1p6	s1p5	s1p1	s1p3	s1p2
s0p5	s0p3	s0p4	s0p2	s0p6	s0p1	s1p5	s1p3	s1p4	s1p2	s1p6	s1p1
s0p6	s0p4	s0p2	s0p3	s0p1	s0p5	s1p6	s1p4	s1p2	s1p3	s1p1	s1p5
s1p1	s1p2	s1p3	s1p4	s1p5	s1p6	s0p1	s0p2	s0p3	s0p4	s0p5	s0p6
s1p2	s1p1	s1p6	s1p5	s1p4	s1p3	s0p2	s0p1	s0p6	s0p5	s0p4	s0p3
s1p3	s1p5	s1p1	s1p6	s1p2	s1p4	s0p3	s0p5	s0p1	s0p6	s0p2	s0p4
s1p4	s1p6	s1p5	s1p1	s1p3	s1p2	s0p4	s0p6	s0p5	s0p1	s0p3	s0p2
s1p5	s1p3	s1p4	s1p2	s1p6	s1p1	s0p5	s0p3	s0p4	s0p2	s0p6	s0p1
s1p6	s1p4	s1p2	s1p3	s1p1	s1p5	s0p6	s0p4	s0p2	s0p3	s0p1	s0p5

*	p2s0	p3s0	p4s0	p5s0	p6s0	p1s1	p3s1	p4s1	p5s1	p6s1
p2s0	s0p1	p6s0	p5s0	p4s0	p3s0	s1p2	p6s1	p5s1	p4s1	p3s1
p3s0	p5s0	s0p1	p6s0	p2s0	p4s0	p3s1	p1s1	p6s1	s1p2	p4s1
p4s0	p6s0	p5s0	s0p1	p3s0	p2s0	p4s1	p5s1	p1s1	p3s1	s1p2
p5s0	p3s0	p4s0	p2s0	p6s0	s0p1	p5s1	p4s1	s1p2	p6s1	p1s1
p6s0	p4s0	p2s0	p3s0	s0p1	p5s0	p6s1	s1p2	p3s1	p1s1	p5s1
p1s1	s1p2	p3s1	p4s1	p5s1	p6s1	s0p1	p3s0	p4s0	p5s0	p6s0
p3s1	p5s1	p1s1	p6s1	s1p2	p4s1	p3s0	s0p1	p6s0	p2s0	p4s0
p4s1	p6s1	p5s1	p1s1	p3s1	s1p2	p4s0	p5s0	s0p1	p3s0	p2s0
p5s1	p3s1	p4s1	s1p2	p6s1	p1s1	p5s0	p4s0	p2s0	p6s0	s0p1
p6s1	p4s1	s1p2	p3s1	p1s1	p5s1	p6s0	p2s0	p3s0	s0p1	p5s0

Next, the full commutation table, with an unusual and appealing double-butterfly pattern.

[.,.]	s0 p2	s0 p3	s0 p4	s0 p5	s0 p6	s1 p1	s1 p2	s1 p3	s1 p4	s1 p5	s1 p6	p2 s0	p3 s0	p4 s0	p5 s0	p6 s0	p1 s1	p3 s1	p4 s1	p5 s1	p6 s1			
s0p2	0					0	0																	
s0p3		0				0		0												0	0			
s0p4			0			0			0											0				
s0p5				0	0	0				0	0													
s0p6				0	0	0				0	0													
s1p1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				0	0			0	0				
s1p2	0					0	0					0							0					
s1p3		0				0		0																
s1p4			0			0			0											0				
s1p5				0	0	0				0	0													
s1p6				0	0	0				0	0													
p2s0							0					0								0				
p3s0													0							0	0			
p4s0														0					0		0			
p5s0					0										0	0	0					0	0	
p6s0					0										0	0	0						0	0
p1s1							0					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
p3s1			0			0							0							0	0			
p4s1		0				0								0						0		0		
p5s1		0													0	0	0					0		
p6s1															0	0	0						0	

Now, on to spawning S_6 .

Three complement pairs actually added up to the matrix of all 1's:

(s0p1+s1p2)+(s0p5+s1p3)+(s0p6+s1p4) -> U1
 (s0p2+s1p1)+(s0p3+s1p5)+(s0p4+s1p6) -> U2
 (p1s0+p2s1)+(p5s0+p3s1)+(p6s0+p4s1) -> U3
 (p2s0+p1s1)+(p3s0+p5s1)+(p4s0+p6s1) -> U4

The box below shows the parent matrix-to-tag correspondence.

U1		U2		U3		U4	
s0p1	123456	s0p2	321654	p1s0	123456	p2s0	563412
s1p2	654321	s1p1	456123	p2s1	654321	p1s1	214365
-----		-----		-----		-----	
s0p5	231564	s0p3	213546	p5s0	345612	p3s0	341256
s1p3	546213	s1p5	564231	p3s1	432165	p5s1	436521
-----		-----		-----		-----	
s0p6	312645	s0p4	132465	p6s0	561234	p4s0	125634
s1p4	465132	s1p6	645312	p4s1	216543	p6s1	652143

The four U-matrices and their transpose T-matrices are shown below for reference.

U ₁	U ₂	U ₃	U ₄	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄
(123456)	(321654)	(123456)	(563412)	(162534)	(342516)	(163452)	(523416)
(654321)	(456123)	(654321)	(214365)	(253416)	(251634)	(254361)	(614325)
(231564)	(213546)	(345612)	(341256)	(341625)	(163425)	(345216)	(341652)
(546213)	(564231)	(432165)	(436521)	(435261)	(615243)	(436125)	(432561)
(312645)	(132465)	(561234)	(125634)	(526143)	(524361)	(521634)	(165234)
(465132)	(645312)	(216543)	(652143)	(614352)	(436152)	(612543)	(256143)

These were used in extensive (yet automated) column-swap operations, both single and double, to eventually generate the entire 720 members of S_6 ; a large number of duplicates resulted from this brute-force approach, though no effort was made to optimize the overall process.

The full list follows, sorted into six groups of 120 entries, each group arranged in a table of 12 x 10 tags corresponding to elements beginning with 1, 2, ..., 6. As explained above, the matrix equivalent to every tag is easily determined; obviously, these are not presented here!

123456	125346	132456	135246	142356	145236	152346	154236	162345	164235
123465	125364	132465	135264	142365	145263	152364	154263	162354	164253
123546	125436	132546	135426	142536	145326	152436	154326	162435	164325
123564	125463	132564	135462	142563	145362	152463	154362	162453	164352
123645	125634	132645	135624	142635	145623	152634	154623	162534	164523
123654	125643	132654	135642	142653	145632	152643	154632	162543	164532
124356	126345	134256	136245	143256	146235	153246	156234	163245	165234
124365	126354	134265	136254	143265	146253	153264	156243	163254	165243
124536	126435	134526	136425	143526	146325	153426	156324	163425	165324
124563	126453	134562	136452	143562	146352	153462	156342	163452	165342
124635	126534	134625	136524	143625	146523	153624	156423	163524	165423
124653	126543	134652	136542	143652	146532	153642	156432	163542	165432

213456	215346	231456	235146	241356	245136	251346	254136	261345	264135
213465	215364	231465	235164	241365	245163	251364	254163	261354	264153
213546	215436	231546	235416	241536	245316	251436	254316	261435	264315
213564	215463	231564	235461	241563	245361	251463	254361	261453	264351
213645	215634	231645	235614	241635	245613	251634	254613	261534	264513
213654	215643	231654	235641	241653	245631	251643	254631	261543	264531
214356	216345	234156	236145	243156	246135	253146	256134	263145	265134
214365	216354	234165	236154	243165	246153	253164	256143	263154	265143
214536	216435	234516	236415	243516	246315	253416	256314	263415	265314
214563	216453	234561	236451	243561	246351	253461	256341	263451	265341
214635	216534	234615	236514	243615	246513	253614	256413	263514	265413
214653	216543	234651	236541	243651	246531	253641	256431	263541	265431

312456	315246	321456	325146	341256	345126	351246	354126	361245	364125
312465	315264	321465	325164	341265	345162	351264	354162	361254	364152
312546	315426	321546	325416	341526	345216	351426	354216	361425	364215
312564	315462	321564	325461	341562	345261	351462	354261	361452	364251
312645	315624	321645	325614	341625	345612	351624	354612	361524	364512
312654	315642	321654	325641	341652	345621	351642	354621	361542	364521
314256	316245	324156	326145	342156	346125	352146	356124	362145	365124
314265	316254	324165	326154	342165	346152	352164	356142	362154	365142
314526	316425	324516	326415	342516	346215	352416	356214	362415	365214
314562	316452	324561	326451	342561	346251	352461	356241	362451	365241
314625	316524	324615	326514	342615	346512	352614	356412	362514	365412
314652	316542	324651	326541	342651	346521	352641	356421	362541	365421

412356	415236	421356	425136	431256	435126	451236	453126	461235	463125
412365	415263	421365	425163	431265	435162	451263	453162	461253	463152
412536	415326	421536	425316	431526	435216	451326	453216	461325	463215
412563	415362	421563	425361	431562	435261	451362	453261	461352	463251
412635	415623	421635	425613	431625	435612	451623	453612	461523	463512
412653	415632	421653	425631	431652	435621	451632	453621	461532	463521
413256	416235	423156	426135	432156	436125	452136	456123	462135	465123
413265	416253	423165	426153	432165	436152	452163	456132	462153	465132
413526	416325	423516	426315	432516	436215	452316	456213	462315	465213
413562	416352	423561	426351	432561	436251	452361	456231	462351	465231
413625	416523	423615	426513	432615	436512	452613	456312	462513	465312
413652	416532	423651	426531	432651	436521	452631	456321	462531	465321

512346	514236	521346	524136	531246	534126	541236	543126	561234	563124
512364	514263	521364	524163	531264	534162	541263	543162	561243	563142
512436	514326	521436	524316	531426	534216	541326	543216	561324	563214
512463	514362	521463	524361	531462	534261	541362	543261	561342	563241
512634	514623	521634	524613	531624	534612	541623	543612	561423	563412
512643	514632	521643	524631	531642	534621	541632	543621	561432	563421
513246	516234	523146	526134	532146	536124	542136	546123	562134	564123
513264	516243	523164	526143	532164	536142	542163	546132	562143	564132
513426	516324	523416	526314	532416	536214	542316	546213	562314	564213
513462	516342	523461	526341	532461	536241	542361	546231	562341	564231
513624	516423	523614	526413	532614	536412	542613	546312	562413	564312
513642	516432	523641	526431	532641	536421	542631	546321	562431	564321

612345	614235	621345	624135	631245	634125	641235	643125	651234	653124
612354	614253	621354	624153	631254	634152	641253	643152	651243	653142
612435	614325	621435	624315	631425	634215	641325	643215	651324	653214
612453	614352	621453	624351	631452	634251	641352	643251	651342	653241
612534	614523	621534	624513	631524	634512	641523	643512	651423	653412
612543	614532	621543	624531	631542	634521	641532	643521	651432	653421
613245	615234	623145	625134	632145	635124	642135	645123	652134	654123
613254	615243	623154	625143	632154	635142	642153	645132	652143	654132
613425	615324	623415	625314	632415	635214	642315	645213	652314	654213
613452	615342	623451	625341	632451	635241	642351	645231	652341	654231
613524	615423	623514	625413	632514	635412	642513	645312	652413	654312
613542	615432	623541	625431	632541	635421	642531	645321	652431	654321

A spreadsheet containing these tags is available upon request; the six groups are plotted in the images below, showing as usual a step-wise pattern.

A hybrid method introduced in [2], wherein a set of lead tags first determined through column-swapping followed by circulant evolution, would also work here to fill out S_6 . For example, the source tag [123456] generates 10 additional tags through the swaps:

S	2↔3	2↔4	2↔5	2↔6	3↔4	3↔5	3↔6	4↔5	4↔6	5↔6
123456	132456	143256	153426	163452	124356	125436	126453	123546	123654	123465

A sequence of iterations – with duplicate removal – would be needed to complete the 120 tag-set, preparatory to circulant evolution.

A different path is to use the hybrid in reverse: circulant evolution first on selected source tags, followed by column swapping. The results are shown below.

S	2↔3	2↔4	2↔5	2↔6	3↔4	3↔5	3↔6	4↔5	4↔6	5↔6
123456	132456	143256	153426	163452	124356	125436	126453	123546	123654	123465
134562	143562	154362	164532	124563	135462	136542	132564	134652	134265	134526
145623	154623	165423	125643	135624	146523	142653	143625	145263	145326	145632
156234	165234	126534	136254	146235	152634	153264	154236	156324	156432	156243
162345	126345	132645	142365	152346	163245	164325	165342	162435	162543	162354
132456	123456	142356	152436	162453	134256	135426	136452	132546	132654	132465
124563	142563	154263	164523	134562	125463	126543	123564	124653	124365	124536
145632	154632	165432	135642	125634	146532	143652	142635	145362	145236	145623
156324	165324	136524	126354	146325	153624	152364	154326	156234	156423	156342
163245	136245	123645	143265	153246	162345	164235	165243	163425	163542	163254

This first pass missed 20 tags, but these were recovered (in red below) unfortunately together with quite a few duplicates.

S	2↔3	2↔4	2↔5	2↔6	3↔4	3↔5	3↔6	4↔5	4↔6	5↔6
134256	143256	124356	154236	164253	132456	135246	136254	134526	134652	134265
142563	124563	152463	162543	132564	145263	146523	143562	142653	142365	142536
125634	152634	165234	135624	145632	126534	123654	124635	125364	125436	125643
156342	165342	136542	146352	126345	153642	154362	152346	156432	156243	156324
163425	136425	143625	123465	153426	164325	162435	165423	163245	163524	163452
124356	142356	134256	154326	164352	123456	125346	126354	124536	124653	124365
143562	134562	153462	163542	123564	145362	146532	142563	143652	143265	143526
135624	153624	165324	125634	145623	136524	132654	134625	135264	135426	135642
156243	165243	126543	146253	136245	152643	154263	153246	156423	156342	156234
162435	126435	142635	132465	152436	164235	163425	165432	162345	162534	162453

Still, this set is now ready for evolving the rest of S_6 though circulant operations using the 'circshift' command. For example, the vector tag [1 3 2 4 5 6] generates five others through

for n=1:6,tags(:,n)=circshift([1 3 2 4 5 6],n-1);end,tags'

```

1 3 2 4 5 6
6 1 3 2 4 5
5 6 1 3 2 4
4 5 6 1 3 2
2 4 5 6 1 3
3 2 4 5 6 1

```

References

- [1] A. Cusmariu, 'S₄ once over easy', 10.5281/zenodo.10613871, 2024.
- [2] A. Cusmariu, 'S₅: piece of cake, almost', 10.5281/zenodo.10630735, 2024.